

Combining Continuous 3D Textiles and Synthetic Microfibres in Textile Reinforced Cements (TRCs): An Evaluation of the Tensile Response and Crack Formation

Ciska Gielis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Belgium, Ciska.Gielis@vub.be
Michael El Kadi, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Belgium, Michael.El.Kadi@vub.be
Didier Snoeck, Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Belgium, Didier.Snoeck@ulb.be
Tine Tysmans, Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Belgium, Tine.Tysmans@vub.be

ABSTRACT

In the presented research, the mechanical response and cracking behaviour of 3D Textile Reinforced Cements (3D TRCs) with integrated microfibres were characterised in tension for the first time, using Digital Image Correlation (DIC). 3D TRCs with and without microfibres, as well as cement matrix reinforced with only microfibres, were studied. The selected microfibres are 6 mm length polypropylene (PP) fibres, added with a volume fraction of 1.0 v%. The addition of short fibres resulted in an enhanced post-cracking stiffness and load-bearing capacity. Moreover, improved cracking behaviour was noted with more and narrower cracks.

KEYWORDS

Textile Reinforced Cement (TRC); 3D Textiles; Polypropylene (PP) fibres; Tensile Characterisation; Digital Image Correlation (DIC)

INTRODUCTION

Textile Reinforced Cements (TRCs) (Peled et al., 2017) have proven to be a feasible, material-efficient alternative to traditional steel-reinforced concrete. However, as TRCs are cementitious materials, they are prone to the formation of (micro-)cracks caused by tensile stresses. These cracks allow for water and harmful substances to infiltrate the interior of the structural material, possibly causing decay and durability-related issues. Research has shown that an improved and controlled crack formation can be achieved in cementitious materials by adding short microfibres into the mixture (Li et al., 2001; Li, 2003; Snoeck & De Belie, 2015). Although these short fibres are not capable to carry large tensile stresses, they can significantly reduce the width of the formed cracks by effectively bridging the cracks and transferring the loads across the crack opening (Li, 1993). In this way, a multiple-cracking behaviour is achieved, resulting in the formation of many cracks with a smaller width that allow for more straightforward repairing possibilities. The addition of polypropylene (PP) fibres to cementitious material has shown to result in efficient multiple-cracking behaviour (Snoeck & De Belie, 2015).

The integration of short fibres into the cementitious matrix of TRCs with planar textile reinforcements (2D textiles) has already been explored. Regarding tensile properties, it was found that the short fibres can result in an increased first-cracking stress and load-bearing capacity (Barhum & Mechtcherine, 2012, 2013; Hinzen & Brameshuber, 2007). Furthermore, TRCs with integrated microfibres demonstrated improved ductility and cracking behaviour, resulting in more and narrower cracks (Barhum & Mechtcherine, 2012, 2013; Hinzen & Brameshuber, 2007). The addition of short fibres to TRCs in which 3D textile reinforcement is used (3D TRCs) has not been studied yet. 3D textiles are composed of two layers of 2D textiles, which are connected by transversal fibres, as shown in Figure 1a. Due to their three-dimensional integrity, 3D textile reinforcement provides more straightforward manufacturing possibilities in comparison with 2D textile reinforcement (Naaman, 2010). Moreover, 3D TRCs have demonstrated improved flexural properties compared to 2D TRCs due to the anchorage mechanism provided by the transversal fibres connecting the textile layers, as well as an improved crack formation (Amzaleg et al., 2013; El Kadi et al., 2019; Haik et al., 2017; Sasi & Peled, 2015). This crack formation could be improved further by adding short fibres to the cementitious matrix.

In this paper, the tensile mechanical properties and cracking behaviour of 3D TRCs with integrated polypropylene (PP) microfibrils are explored. By means of tensile tests monitored through Digital Image Correlation (DIC) (Schreier et al., 2009), the tensile properties and crack formation were investigated of 3D TRCs with and without integrated microfibrils, as well as cementitious material with only microfibre reinforcement. Specimens were monitored on both sides, allowing for an investigation of possible asymmetry in tensile response and cracking behaviour, especially for the 3D TRC configuration with integrated microfibrils to evaluate the distribution of fibres throughout the cross-section.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Textiles and short fibres

The used textiles are commercially available knitted 3D textiles (SitGrid 701, Wilhelm Kneitz AG, Germany), shown in Figure 1a. These textiles are formed by two planar layers of AR-glass textiles (2400 tex; mesh size: 22.5 mm by 22.5 mm) that are transversally connected by means of polyester fibres that ensure a distance of 8.5 mm between the two textile layers. The textiles are coated with styrene-butadiene (SBR). The studied short fibres are commercially available polypropylene (PP) fibres with a length of 6 mm (Redco, Belgium), illustrated in Figure 1b.

Figure 1: (a) 3D textile reinforcement composed of two layers of AR-glass textiles connected by transversal polyester fibres. (b) 6 mm length polypropylene (PP) fibres.

Table 1: Material properties of the used 3D textiles (SitGrid 701, Wilhelm Kneitz AG, Germany) (El Kadi et al., 2019) and the selected PP fibres (Redco, Belgium) (De Lhoneux et al., 2002).

Reinforcement	Fabric density [g/m ²]	Specific gravity [g/cm ³]	Yarn stiffness [GPa]	Yarn failure stress [MPa]
3D textiles	616 (coated) 536 (uncoated)	2.68	67	496

Reinforcement	Length [mm]	Specific gravity [g/cm ³]	Young's modulus [GPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]
PP fibres	6	0.91	11.6	928

Cementitious matrix

The applied mortar mixture for the cementitious matrix is composed of Portland cement (CEM I 52.2 N, Holcim, Belgium), fly ash (Microsit, BauMineral GmbH, Germany), quartz sand (M34, Sibelco, Belgium), water and superplasticizer (MasterGlenium 51, BASF, Netherlands), following the ratios given in Table 2.

Table 2: Matrix composition: densities and mass ratios with respect to the binder (cement + fly ash).

	Binder	Cement	Fly ash	Sand	Water	Superplasticizer
Density [kg/m ³]	/	3140	2550	2650	1000	1100
Ratio [kg/kg]	1	0.50	0.50	0.35	0.30	0.008

Methods

Material configurations and manufacturing process

Specimens with either 3D textile reinforcement or microfibre reinforcement were investigated, as well as specimens with a combination of the two reinforcement types. In the configurations with 3D textile reinforcement, the effective volume fraction (in the loading direction) of the 3D textiles (V_{tex}^*) was 0.7 v%. During casting, the flow of the fibre-mortar mixture can be hindered by the 3D textile reinforcement, which can result in a significantly uneven distribution of short fibres throughout the cross-section of the TRC element. The penetration of the fibre-mortar mixture through the 3D textile meshes is linked with the fibre content, type, and length. For the studied PP fibres with a length of 6 mm, it was visually assessed that sufficient penetration through the 3D textiles could be achieved when the fibres were added to the cementitious matrix with a fibre volume fraction (V_f) of 1.0 v% with regard to the total volume of the mould (Gielis et al., 2023). Thus, in the configurations with microfibre reinforcement, this V_f was adopted. Both sides of the specimens were monitored, the side that was facing the mould surface during casting and the side that was facing the direction from which the fibre-mortar mixture was casted. By doing so, possible differences between the mould-side and the casting-side surfaces could be investigated, especially for the 3D TRC configuration with integrated fibres as a possible uneven distribution of fibres throughout the cross-section of the samples could lead to different results when comparing the two sides.

For each of the three material configurations, an analogue manufacturing method was applied, of which the casting stage is illustrated in Figure 2. The specimens were produced using moulds with a length of 500 mm, a width of 60 mm and a depth of 15 mm. For the configurations with 3D textile reinforcement (with or without integrated microfibres), the moulds allowed for the textiles to be clamped in place to ensure a cover thickness of 2 mm on both sides of the test samples. For the configuration with only microfibre reinforcement, similar moulds were used, but as there was no textile reinforcement clamping was not required. Once the moulds were prepared, the mortar mixture with or without integrated microfibres was casted until the textile reinforcement, if present, was fully embedded and the moulds were filled. During casting the mixture was vibrated to remove air bubbles from the cementitious matrix. For each configuration, six specimens were produced. They were covered with plastic foil and stored in standard laboratory conditions.

Figure 2: Casting process of 3D TRC with 1.0 v% PP fibres (6 mm) added to the cementitious matrix.

Tensile test setup

After 28 days of curing, the specimens could be tested in tension, using the test setup illustrated in Figure 3. This setup is based on RILEM recommendations (Bramshuber, 2016), but it must be noted that some adaptations were made following the research of El Kadi et al. (El Kadi et al., 2019). The uniaxial tensile test setup consists of two clamps, composed of steel plates, in between which the specimens are installed. By tightening the six bolts that are provided in each of the clamps, the specimens are clamped in between the steel plates. Before tightening, rubber sheets are placed between the surfaces of the specimens and the steel plates to protect the specimens and establish a uniform distribution of stress. Additionally, to prevent the specimens from slipping, a steel pin is added to each of the clamps, going through the test specimens. The tests were conducted on an Instron 5885 test bench. An upwards displacement with a rate of 1 mm/min was appointed to the upper clamp. To precisely monitor the displacement and strain fields two DIC systems were used, one for the specimen surface that was facing the mould surface during casting (M.S.) and one for the specimen surface that was facing the side from which the fibre-mortar mixture was casted (C.S). Both sides were painted white, and a speckle pattern was applied. Cameras with a pixel density of 2448 by 2048 pixels, and lenses of 12 and 17 mm were used.

Figure 3: (a) Schematic view of the tensile test setup. (b) Real tensile test setup with DIC monitoring at both sides of the test specimens.

Analysis

Concerning the analysis, a distinction must be made between the data derived from the DIC systems and the data derived from the test bench. For the two 3D TRC configurations, a DIC analysis was carried out, in which a subset, step and window strain size of 21 px, 7 px and 9 data points were used, respectively. This DIC analysis was, however, not appropriate for the configuration with only microfibre reinforcement due to failure after the first crack in the clamps. For this reason, the displacement and strain fields monitored by the DIC systems during mechanical loading did not correctly represent the material's behaviour. In this case, only the data derived from the test bench was used to analyse the tensile response, but it must be noted that this data is not as accurate as the DIC data. Nonetheless, it does give an idea of the tensile behaviour of the material with only 1.0 v% of microfibre reinforcement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile mechanical response

The results of the tensile tests are presented in Figure 4 and Table 3. In Figure 4, the stress (σ) is demonstrated as a function of the strain (ϵ). For the 3D TRC configurations with and without integrated PP fibres, the stress-strain curves are provided for both the mould-side surface and the casting-side surface as they were derived from the DIC analysis. For the configuration with only fibres, only one set of stress-strain curves is provided as they were derived from the data generated by the test bench.

Figure 4: Stress-strain curves derived through DIC analysis of both the mould-side surface (M.S.) and the casting-side surface (C.S.): (a and b) 3D TRC + PP fibres and (c and d) 3D TRC. Stress-strain curves derived through analysis of test bench data: (e) cementitious matrix with only PP fibres.

In Table 3, the average values and standard deviations are provided for the first-cracking stress (σ_c), the failure stress (σ_f), and the pre-cracking and post-cracking stiffnesses (respectively E_1 and E_3). As already explained, the tensile properties of the configuration with only microfibre reinforcement were derived from the data generated by the test bench. For the 3D TRC configurations (with and without added microfibres), the data derived from the DIC systems was used. Regarding the pre-cracking properties (σ_c and E_1), the first-cracking stress (σ_c) was considered the highest stress before the first drop in stress, which indicated the formation of the first crack. The pre-cracking stiffness (E_1) was measured in the zone between the start of mechanical loading and the point at which the first-cracking stress (σ_c) was

reached. As expected for cementitious material reinforced with only short fibres, there was strain-softening after the formation of the first crack. Hence, no post-cracking properties are reported for that configuration. The stress-strain curves of the 3D TRCs with integrated microfibrils are bilinear, which is in line with the research of Hinzen and Brameshuber (Hinzen & Brameshuber, 2009) on 2D TRCs with integrated short fibres. The stress-strain curves of the 3D TRCs without integrated microfibrils are bilinear as well, but it can already be noted that the load-bearing capacity remained more or less the same after the formation of the first crack. For the 3D TRC configurations (with and without microfibrils), the failure stress (σ_f) was considered as the highest reached stress, and the post-cracking stiffness (E_3) was measured using the linear regression of the curves between the points at which the first-cracking stress (σ_c) and failure stress (σ_f) were respectively reached.

Table 3: Average values and standard deviations of experimentally determined tensile properties (σ_c , E_1 , σ_f and E_3) for the three studied material configurations.

Conf.	n	Side	σ_c [MPa]		E_1 [MPa]		σ_f [MPa]		E_3 [MPa]	
			avg.	st.dev.	avg.	st.dev.	avg.	st.dev.	avg.	st.dev.
3D + PP	6	M.S.	2.24	0.43	16460	7752	5.27	0.60	120.05	11.07
		C.S.	2.28	0.35	10453	2262	5.27	0.60	115.90	8.46
3D	6	M.S.	2.04	0.73	9306	7666	4.24	0.13	72.65	17.96
		C.S.	2.33	0.57	9579	7789	4.24	0.13	74.25	28.29
PP	6	/	2.09	0.65	869	115	/	/	/	/

The first-cracking stress (σ_c) was similar for all studied configurations. For the two 3D TRC configurations, no significant differences in the average σ_c were noted when the mould-side surface was compared to the casting-side surface. Regarding the pre-cracking stiffnesses (E_1), the two 3D TRC configurations and the configuration only reinforced with fibres could not be compared, as the data of the last one was not derived through DIC. When comparing the two 3D TRC configurations to each other, no clear conclusions could be derived as there was a large scatter in results. This was possibly due to cracks that were prematurely present in the samples as a result of the clamping process.

As could be expected, no significant differences were noted in the average values of the post-cracking properties (σ_f and E_3) between the mould-side surface and the casting-side surface of the specimens of one 3D TRC configuration (with or without integrated microfibrils). However, it must be remarked that, when comparing the individual curves between one face and the other, there are some noticeable differences. This could indicate that, at crack formation (sudden decrease in stress), the cracks did not immediately propagate across the entire thickness of the specimens, but rather started at one side. When comparing the two configurations to each other, considerable differences were observed. Upon the addition of 1.0 v% of PP fibres, the stress at failure (σ_c) increased from 4.24 ± 0.13 MPa to 5.27 ± 0.60 MPa for both sides of the specimens, an average increase of 24%. The predominant failure mechanism was failure of the 3D textile fibres, both for the 3D TRC specimens with and without integrated microfibrils (see Figure 5). The post-cracking stiffness (E_3) increased as well, from 74.25 ± 28.29 MPa to 115.90 ± 8.46 MPa when the casting-side surface is considered, an average increase of 56%. These results are in line with what has been found concerning the addition of short fibres to 2D TRCs (Barhum & Mechtcherine, 2012, 2013; Hinzen & Brameshuber, 2007).

Figure 5: Failure of the 3D textile fibres as the predominant failure mechanism for the 3D TRC configurations (a) without and (b) with integrated short fibres.

Crack formation

Through DIC monitoring, the displacement and strain fields were monitored for the two 3D TRC configurations with and without integrated microfibres. Both the mould-side surface and the casting-side surface were monitored. By doing so, possible differences in the crack formation at the two sides of the specimens could be observed.

The results of the crack formation analysis are summarised in Table 4. At a strain of 1.5%, the crack widths and spacings were measured on a line drawn in the centre of the specimen, parallel to the specimen's edges. However, for some 3D TRC specimens without added microfibres, spalling was observed, which lead to correlation losses in the DIC analysis software. For this reason, it was not always possible to measure the crack widths and spacings on the central line. Cracks located in these zones of correlation loss could not be recorded, so an additional line was drawn through a zone with correlation, and the cracks were measured on this line. An analysis of the crack opening evolution over the width of a representative specimen was carried out to provide perspective to this decision. The opening of a crack was measured in the centre, as well as at the left and right edge of the specimen's width, as shown in Figure 6. With respect to the crack width measured in the centre, relative differences of -15% and +18% were respectively measured with the left edge and the right edge.

Figure 6: To assess the evolution of the crack opening over the width of a specimen, a crack was measured in the centre as well as at the left and right edge of the specimen's surface.

Table 4: Average values and standard deviations of the number of cracks, the average crack spacing, and the average and maximum crack width in 3D TRC specimens with and without integrated microfibres, measured at 1.5 % strain.

Conf.	n	Side	No. of cracks		Avg. crack spacing [mm]		Avg. crack width [μ m]		Max. crack width [μ m]	
			avg.	st.dev.	avg.	st.dev.	avg.	st.dev.	avg.	st.dev.
3D + PP	6	M.S.	13.33	2.75	16.73	9.55	255	161	597	116
		C.S.	19.50	3.59	11.35	9.88	163	97	430	157
3D	6	M.S.	6.00	1.15	35.62	32.05	590	409	1253	201
		C.S.	5.00	2.00	35.27	23.92	629	329	1093	218

When comparing the crack formation at the mould-side and casting-side surfaces to each other for each of the two 3D TRC configurations, some noticeable differences were observed. In Figure 7, the DIC images of both sides of selected representative specimens are illustrated. The 3D TRC configuration without integrated microfibres did not show significant differences between its two sides in the number of cracks, crack spacing and crack width. Meanwhile, generally, a higher number of cracks, smaller crack spacings and more narrow crack widths were observed at the casting-side surface of the 3D TRC specimens with integrated fibres compared to the mould-side surface. These differences could indicate a hampered penetration of the fibre-mortar mixture through the 3D textile reinforcement, hence an uneven distribution of short fibres throughout the material's cross-section. However, the differences remain within the margins of error when looking at the standard deviations. Moreover, the uneven distribution could be exploited as an advantage by orienting the structural elements in such a way that the highest amount of short fibres is located in the zone with the highest tensile stresses.

A comparison between the two 3D TRC configurations demonstrated the positive influence of the integration of short fibres on the material's cracking behaviour, in addition to its positive effect on the tensile properties. The largest differences were noted when comparing the casting-side surfaces of the 3D TRC specimens with and without integrated microfibres. In Figure 7 (c and d), the DIC images of this side of two representative specimens are illustrated. From Table 4, it can be deduced that, upon the addition of 1.0 v% of PP fibres, the number of cracks increased from 5.00 ± 2.00 cracks to 19.50 ± 3.59 cracks, a number that is almost four times as high. With regard to the average crack spacing, the differences are not as clear due to large standard deviations. However, from the average values, it can be seen that the 3D TRC material with integrated short fibres generally demonstrated smaller crack spacings, which could as well be expected due to the higher number of cracks. At the casting-side surface, the average crack width decreased from $629 \pm 329 \mu\text{m}$ to $163 \pm 97 \mu\text{m}$. The large standard deviations of the average crack width in the 3D TRC material without integrated microfibres compared to the 3D TRC material with integrated microfibres must be noted as well. Finally, the maximum crack width was also significantly smaller when short fibres were added. A decrease from $1093 \pm 218 \mu\text{m}$ to $430 \pm 157 \mu\text{m}$ was measured. This generally improved cracking behaviour as a result of the addition of microfibres to the cementitious matrix of 3D TRCs is in line with the research that has already been carried out on 2D TRCs with integrated short fibres (Barhum & Mechtcherine, 2012, 2013; Hinzen & Brameshuber, 2007).

Figure 7: DIC images of two representative test samples, showing the crack patterns and longitudinal strains at an average strain of 1.5%: (a) 3D TRC and (b) 3D TRC + PP fibres at the mould-side surface (M.S.); (c) 3D TRC and (d) 3D TRC + PP fibres at the casting-side surface (M.S.).

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the tensile mechanical response and related crack formation of 3D Textile Reinforced Cements (TRCs) with integrated microfibres were explored. This was done by comparing three material configurations: 3D TRC without integrated microfibres, 3D TRC with 1.0 v% of PP fibres (6 mm), and cementitious material only reinforced with 1.0 v% of PP fibres. Through tensile tests monitored by DIC on both sides of the specimens, the tensile properties and cracking behaviour of the three configurations were studied.

Regarding the tensile mechanical response, it must be noted that the cementitious material only reinforced with short fibres demonstrated a strain-softening behaviour, so no post-cracking properties could be reported. A comparison with the other two configurations was not possible. With regard to the two 3D TRC configurations (with and without integrated fibres), no notable differences were observed when comparing the average values of the post-cracking properties of the mould-side and the casting-side surfaces to each other. However, significant differences were observed when comparing the two configurations to each other. The 3D TRC with 1.0 v% of PP fibres integrated into the cementitious matrix achieved an increased post-cracking stiffness and a higher stress at failure. Concerning the cracking behaviour, an improvement was noted as well upon the addition of the short PP fibres. The 3D TRC with integrated microfibres generally showed a higher number of cracks, with reduced crack spacings and more narrow crack widths. A notable difference was also observed in the crack formation of the mould-side surface and the casting-side surface of the 3D TRCs with integrated microfibres, which could indicate a hampered penetration of the fibre-mortar mixture through the 3D textile reinforcement.

Cementitious material has the ability to heal formed cracks through self-healing, but only if they remain narrow enough. Thus, in future research, this possibility could be explored for 3D TRCs with integrated short fibres, as the improved cracking behaviour could potentially activate the material's self-healing properties.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- Amzaleg, E., Peled, A., Janetzko, S., & Gries, T. (2013). Flexural behavior of cement based element reinforced with 3D fabric. In J. G. M. Van Mier, G. Ruiz, C. Andrade, R. C. Yu, & X. X. Zhang (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Fracture Mechanics of Concrete and Concrete Structures (FraMCoS-8)* (pp. 1080-1088). International Center for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE).
- Barhum, R., & Mechtcherine, V. (2012). Effect of short, dispersed glass and carbon fibres on the behaviour of textile-reinforced concrete under tensile loading. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 92, 56-71. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2012.06.001>
- Barhum, R., & Mechtcherine, V. (2013). Influence of short dispersed and short integral glass fibres on the mechanical behaviour of textile-reinforced concrete. *Materials and Structures*, 46(4), 557-572. <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-012-9913-3>
- Brameshuber, W. (2016). Recommendation of RILEM TC 232-TDT: test methods and design of textile reinforced concrete. *Materials and Structures*, 49(12), 4923-4927. <https://doi.org/10.1617/s11527-016-0839-z>
- De Lhoneux, B., Kalbskopf, R., Kim, P., Li, V. C., Lin, Z., Vidts, D., . . . Wu, H.-C. (2002). Development of High Tenacity Polypropylene Fibres for Cementitious Composites. In *Proceedings of the JCI International Workshop on Ductile Fiber Reinforced Cementitious Composites (DFRCC): Application & Evaluation* (pp. 121-132). JCI.
- El Kadi, M., Tysmans, T., Verbruggen, S., Vervloet, J., De Munck, M., Wastiels, J., & Van Hemelrijck, D. (2019). Experimental study and benchmarking of 3D textile reinforced cement composites. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 104, 1-10. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2019.103352>

- Gielis, C., El Kadi, M., Tysmans, T., & Snoeck, D. (2023). Mix Optimisation and Bending Behaviour of Cement Composites Reinforced with 3D Textiles and Microfibres. In M. Kunieda, T. Kanakubo, T. Kanda, & K. Kobayashi (Eds.), *Strain Hardening Cementitious Composites (SHCC5)* (Vol. 39, pp. 209-216). Springer. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-15805-6_22
- Haik, R., Adiel Sasi, E., & Peled, A. (2017). Influence of three-dimensional (3D) fabric orientation on flexural properties of cement-based composites. *Cement and Concrete Composites*, 80, 1-9. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconcomp.2017.02.007>
- Hinzen, M., & Brameshuber, W. (2007). Influence of short fibres on strength, ductility and crack development of textile reinforced concrete. In H. W. Reinhardt & A. E. Naaman (Eds.), *Fifth International RILEM Workshop on High Performance Fiber Reinforced Cement Composites (HPFRCC5)* (pp. 105 - 112). RILEM Publications.
- Hinzen, M., & Brameshuber, W. (2009, June 3-5). *Improvement of Serviceability and Strength of Textile Reinforced Concrete by using Short Fibres* [Paper presentation]. 4th Colloquium on Textile Reinforced Structures (CTRS4), Dresden, Germany. <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:bsz:14-ds-1244046356375-03273>
- Li, V., Wang, S. X., & Wu, C. (2001). Tensile strain-hardening behavior of polyvinyl alcohol engineered cementitious composite (PVA-ECC). *ACI Materials Journal*, 98, 483-492.
- Li, V. C. (1993). From Micromechanics to Structural Engineering - The Design of Cementitious Composites for Civil Engineering Applications. *Journal of Structural Mechanics and Earthquake Engineering*, 10(2), 37-48.
- Li, V. C. (2003). On Engineered Cementitious Composites (ECC) A Review of the Material and Its Applications. *Journal of Advanced Concrete Technology*, 1(3), 215-230.
- Naaman, A. E. (2010). Textile Reinforced Cement Composites: Competitive Status and Research Directions. In W. Brameshuber (Ed.), *International RILEM Conference in Material Science* (Vol. 1, pp. 3 - 22). RILEM Publications SARL.
- Peled, A., Bentur, A., & Mobasher, B. (2017). *Textile Reinforced Concrete* (1st ed.). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315119151>
- Sasi, E. A., & Peled, A. (2015). Three dimensional (3D) fabrics as reinforcements for cement-based composites. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 74, 153-165. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.04.008>
- Schreier, H., Orteu, J.-J., & Sutton, M. A. (2009). *Image Correlation for Shape, Motion and Deformation Measurements* (1 ed.). Springer. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-78747-3>
- Snoeck, D., & De Belie, N. (2015). From straw in bricks to modern use of microfibers in cementitious composites for improved autogenous healing – A review. *Construction and Building Materials*, 95, 774-787. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2015.07.018>